

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPING LINGUISTIC CULTURAL AND COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TRANSLATORS

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Abstract: In this article, the methodological foundations of the development of linguistic cultural and communicative competence of future translators are studied. Linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competences of communicative competence were also analyzed.

Key words: pedagogic, linguistic, communicative, system, improvement, competence, culture, linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic.

INTRODUCTION

Stress-free situations are important in the development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators. The lower the stress, the higher the learning efficiency. Attention should be paid to the equal possession of all components of communicative competence, such as linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competence. For this reason, it is necessary to express the goals in a way that connects the organizational (grammatical, discourse) and pragmatic (functional, sociolinguistic, strategic) aspects of the language.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The issues of developing the linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators have been studied by many scientists of the West, the CIS and our country, and even today this process is systematically implemented. The psychological foundations of the communicative approach are L.S. Vygotsky's "social constructivism", J. Piaget's "cognitive constructivism", A.N. Chomsky's "Critical Period Hypothesis", "Universal Grammar" and "Aspects of Syntax" theories, and J. Bruner's "Scaffolding" (Havoza), K. It is closely related to Johnson and W. Littlewood's "Skills Learning Models".

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In elucidating the essence of methodology principles, work was done based on psychological and linguistic laws and the following psycholinguistic principles were summarized:

Increasing the motivation (internal motivation) of future translators to learn and master a foreign language.

Stimulation of active linguistic and cultural communication of students in classes.

Development of intermediate language (metalanguage) experiences of students.

Teaching students to use the relationship between the native language and the studied foreign language.

Individual approach, that is, conducting psycho-pedagogical activities taking into account the characteristics of students (the nature of each student, what they are capable of, what they are interested in, who they make friends with, what they have a negative attitude towards).

Methodological principles of development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence in future translators are as follows: foreign language teaching methodology, (a)

general (speech orientation, limited and holistic teaching, exercises, taking language experience into account), (b) private (foreign language teaching on the basis of a speech sample, the relationship between language training and speech practice, the interdependence of speech activity types, the advancement of oral speech, getting closer to natural speech in a foreign language, accelerating the elementary stage), (v) special principles (teaching grammar, teaching lexis, teaching reading and using speech writing in teaching a foreign language) have been developed. In summarizing the pedagogical principles, we considered the communicative approach to teaching foreign languages.

Implementation of visual approach and multisensory (fully driving all speech analyzers) learning. That is, a lot of exercises with the participation of analyzers of seeing, hearing, movement (speech, movement and hand) in order to ensure thorough mastering of the educational material.

Holistic (lexical, grammar and pronunciation language material as a whole) teaching.

Speech orientation (perform lexical, grammatical and pronunciation exercises in order to acquire speech activity).

Teaching a foreign language based on speech samples.

The pedagogical principles of developing linguistic, cultural and communicative competence in future translators are as follows:

Bringing the growing generation to maturity in all aspects. The information acquired through the medium of a foreign language and the mental and speech skills and competencies acquired during the study of a foreign language educate students.

Encourage students to use the language being studied.

Taking into account the individual characteristics of students.

Educating students in the spirit of tolerance towards others and respect for different values.

Creating an optimal situation for independent learning of knowledge in lessons.

Forming the skills and abilities of students to independently and mutually determine mastery indicators.

Creating an opportunity for students to demonstrate their knowledge in the language being studied.

Organization of lessons based on an integrative approach aimed at acquisition of competencies.

In modern pedagogy, theories scientifically justifying the objective laws of the development of linguistic and communicative knowledge and skills have been developed [5]:

- proportionality theory - mother tongue and foreign language acquisition processes are exactly similar;
- interlinguistic theory - the characteristics of the educational environment are important in ensuring the successful learning of a foreign language. Both theories are based on the principle of awareness of didactics (understanding the content of the speech and understanding the language units in the structure of the speech) and the process of acquiring linguo-communicative skills is interpreted as a cognitive and creative activity.

According to supporters of the theory of proportionality in the development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence, the processes of mother tongue and second language acquisition are the same [3]. According to this theory, cross-linguistic interference is avoided, and speech patterns are taught as a whole without being separated into parts (phonemes, graphemes, morphemes and words). This approach to teaching a

foreign language is highly effective in an environment where there is a strong need to use the foreign language being studied [4]. Because the process of mastering the elements (components) of a foreign language is exactly similar (parallel) to the process of mastering the mother tongue, i.e. speaking competences first, then linguistic competences or first listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing, then the acquisition of phonetics, lexicon, and grammar happens in sequence [2].

According to the interlinguistic theory in the development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence, all factors affecting the process of learning a foreign language should be taken into account. These factors consist of the age-related (psychological and cognitive activity) characteristics of a foreign language learner, the content and purpose of education, and educational tools developed in accordance with them. According to this theory, in the process of learning a foreign language, a new linguistic system of communication in a foreign language, which the student learns based on language experience, forms a "mixed/interlingual code". That is, the experience of the mother tongue has a positive and negative effect on learning a second language, and then on acquiring a foreign language (interlingual transposition and interference). For this reason, when creating textbooks and programs, cross-linguistic interference and the student's language experience are taken into account, the rules intended for education (simple theoretical knowledge) are subordinated to the goals of accelerating and simplifying the acquisition of practical skills and competencies. That is, some necessary rules or elements of theories are described in order to speed up and facilitate the process of learning a foreign language.

In Uzbekistan, the system of training future translators is directed to the formation of a second language knowledge holder (cognizant), that is, the study of the cultural heritage created by the master of the studied language is the main goal of foreign language education. A second language informant can be understood as a person who has the competence to communicate adequately in a foreign language with a representative of a foreign culture in authentic communication situations. While learning the language, the future translator is not busy with acquiring linguistic knowledge, but with improving his/her speech and cultural skills (competencies). Lingvo-communicative activity is taught on the basis of an integrative approach aimed at the acquisition of competence, focused on the individual. This integrative approach differs from the "Content and Language Integrated Learning" approach in European education. The communicative-cumulative method is applied in the training of future translators. Mutual understanding of interlocutors (communicants) is the main criterion of translation, and for this reason it is possible to temporarily ignore mistakes that do not prevent mutual understanding. A person- and action-oriented communicative approach to translation training based on interlinguistic theory enables future translators to engage in live communication as soon as possible and without fear. Not being afraid of mistakes, serious emphasis on the content of education increases students' enthusiasm for using the studied foreign language. According to this approach, a) psychological and age-related characteristics of the student affect the process of learning a foreign language; b) interlanguage interference; c) educational tools; g) educational institution; d) it is recommended to take into account all factors such as the professional skills of the pedagogue.

Today, representatives of a new generation who think in a new way, who see their future in connection with the strengthening of democratic values in society, the future of our country in the world community, are coming into life. Today's young people are superior in terms of

ability, intelligence, diligence. That is, children strive to fully use their intellectual potential from a very early age and demand strong attention to themselves, try to understand the world around them as quickly as possible.

Human speech is scientifically studied in linguophysiology (speech physiology), speech occurrence and perception in psycholinguistics. In the development of linguistic and cultural competence, the comparative study of such issues as the development processes of phonetic, lexical and grammatical skills is also important.

It is known that teaching a foreign language is the organization of speech or perception processes in this language. The meaning of the term "speech" means the way of forming and expressing an idea, the practical use and realization of language. Language is a means of communication and interaction, a system of signs, a tool, a tool for expressing and forming thoughts [6]. Language is common for people who use it, that is, social speech is an individual phenomenon.

Speech is a complex mental process controlled by the activity of the human brain, and its sound and literal aspects are external (material), speech, movement, hearing, sight, and hand movement are expressed in the symbols of the internal side. Both constitute a dynamic speech stereotype. It is known from the research that dynamic stereotype is understood as a system of coordinated and stabilized signs consisting of conditional and unconditional reflexes. In the native language, character stereotypes and speech mechanisms are formed involuntarily during the formation of thought and speech and operate without the participation of consciousness (more precisely, almost without the participation of consciousness). When learning a foreign language, similar elements (sound, word, sentence structure) based on previously learned languages are created using the existing neural connections, and foreign elements are created using the secondary sign system due to the emergence of new connections [7]. It is known from the studies of L.S. Vygotsky that the development of speech in a foreign language is fundamentally different from the development of speech in the native language. Speech in the native language is not developed purposefully without the participation of consciousness. A child's speech and thinking develop in parallel. That is, the child uses language tools to express the thought formed in his mind and thus begins to understand the existence that surrounds him. Concepts expressed in language are formed in the process of understanding existence. During the development of speech in a foreign language, the picture is completely different. When learning a foreign language, the student acquires to a certain extent language and speech experiences in the native language, as well as the skills to perform basic thinking operations in this language. The acquisition of foreign language units is not compatible with the process of understanding the surrounding existence. In this process, the learner develops not only thinking, but also the ability to adequately use tools and methods of expressing thoughts specific to a foreign language and culture. This, in turn, requires that attention should be paid to the principle of awareness of teaching. That is, language material related to phonetics, lexicon and grammar is methodically prepared and presented for the acquisition of communicative competence [8].

The goals of education aimed at developing linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators in foreign literature are: a) pragmatic or practical goal of communicative (linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic) competences; b) it is recommended that the educational goal should be the acquisition of cultural competences (the cultural heritage of the owner of the foreign language being studied) [1]. According to YE.I. Passov, the

practical goal should be the acquisition of competencies (knowledge, skills and abilities), and the educational goal should be the assimilation of culture. N.D.Galskova and Z.N.Nikitenko define communicative competence as the ability to use a foreign language effectively and confidently in order to understand and present information, and by the term practical purpose, they mean the pragmatic component [5].

CONCLUSION. Based on the above and various definitions given by experts, communicative competence is the ability to communicate effectively to achieve a certain goal, to use language adequately to share information, thoughts, views, thoughts, imagination and inner experiences. It is possible to formulate a definition that it is a set of necessary knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure successful competition with the interlocutor.

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